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Effective Leadership in Decision Making and Mediation in the Relationship Between Educators and Parents: A Case Study of Primary Schools in Western Macedonia, Greece

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Abstract

The quality of leadership exercised within the educational unit is paramount to developing an effective school and enhancing student achievement. The purpose of this paper is to investigate effective leadership in decision-making and mediation in the relationship between teachers and parents in a specific region in Greece. The method of quantitative research with sampling was chosen. The research instrument used was a specially designed questionnaire whose questions were based on other research with similar thematic content. Data entry, processing and analysis were performed using the statistical program IBMStatisticsSPSSversion 21. As for its results, there are two important characteristics that a principal must possess for the effectiveness of his/her interventions in the role of mediator. These characteristics included the participation of parents and teachers in problem solving and the individual briefing and action of the director in order to effectively mediate in the restoration of relationships. What emerged from the factor analysis conducted to highlight the main characteristics that a principal should have in the role of mediator was cooperation, organization, the use of body language, practical applications, character potential, ethics, training and information. Among others, the paper concluded that the principals who take on the role of mediator perceive that their role has a positive response and is efficient for both parents and teachers. On the contrary, deputy principals and teachers who are receivers of the role and not actors, perceive that the response is not positive and the role of the principal does not promote efficiency.

Keywords: Effective Leadership, Decision Making, Mediation, Teachers, Parents

1. Introduction

It is since antiquity that man has been organized into groups in order to achieve common goals. A natural development of cooperation which arises when interests clash is conflict, a typical social phenomenon. Conflicts constitute a characteristic of human life at all levels of social context and are sometimes manifested in the form of

a simple disagreement, sometimes in the form of aggression, and often take the form of passive resistance (Yukl, 2013).

As far as the effective operation of a school organization is concerned, it stems from the effective communication and cooperation among all its members, bodies and factors that make up the school system, as well as the effective communication and cooperation of the school system with the closer or wider social systems. In fact, the quality of leadership exercised within the school unit is paramount to the development of an effective school and the enhancement of student achievement (Hoover-Dempsey, et al., 1999).

The purpose of the paper is to highlight how school principals spend sufficient time in order to resolve various forms of conflict, starting from the individual conflict they experience themselves when making a decision while subsequently they have to face and spend time on the conflicts between colleagues, students and between teachers and parents. The decisions made by the school administration will have a direct impact on the school climate and will affect the productivity of teachers, students and the balance of relationships between school and parents. The wrong management of the school's human resources will affect the achievement of the school unit goals. The main objective of this paper will not be to prove that the reduction of conflicts will constitute the solution for the normalization of the school climate, but how the principal as a leader and mediator will highlight, through the organizational form of mediation as a communication tool, positive elements such as the common goals and purposes and convert any conflict that will s/he be called upon to face into a functional and effective one (Triantari, 2020).

The paper deals with the communication behaviors, skills and strategies of the modern principal of a school unit, who also plays the role of a mediator, whose characteristics are impartiality, reciprocity, balance, justice, respect, seriousness, assistance, composure, empathy, humor. The paper complies with the APA bibliographic system.

The present research is called upon to supplement the findings related to the communication behaviors, skills and strategies of the modern principal within the current context of a mediator. The necessity of the mediation skill as a communication tool will be highlighted through the research, which hopes that it will mobilize the state in training its principals, and in the hard times we are going through due to the economic and social crisis, it will emphasize the prominent importance of effective communication towards optimizing the results of counseling procedures as a tool for normalizing relationships throughout the school community.

The results of the research can be used for further study and reinforcement of the theories of good and successful leadership.

2. Conflicts and types of conflicts in primary education

According to Misla (2012: 25), conflict is defined as "the situation where the behavior of a person or a group intentionally seeks to impede the achievement of another person's or group's goals". On the basis of this definition, it is easily understood that the conflicts which may arise within the educational environment can be either interpersonal, that is, between individuals, or group ones, that is, between two or more different groups.

Therefore, the forms of conflicts in the school environment can take various forms, such as interpersonal or group ones as well as between individuals and groups, even school community conflicts (Henkin & Holliman, 2009). Interpersonal conflicts take place among the school personnel members, for example among school teachers or between teachers and the school principal. Teachers find it difficult to obey principals or follow rules or accept extra work, while principals press them for several school activities, resulting in frequent conflicts between teachers and principals.

Furthermore, intergroup conflicts take place between different groups in the school. Thus, conflicts can be observed between teachers and students and, as informal groups are created in each organization, conflicts also occur between these groups. Conflicts between individuals and groups arise between an individual and a group.

In particular, conflicts may arise between the school principal and the teachers' board or between a teacher and the students of a school class. School community conflicts occur between the school and the local community. The school is an open system interacting with its wider environment. Inevitably, this interaction may lead to conflicts, for example between the teachers' board and the parents' association or the local government.

Therefore, conflicts within a school unit there may comprise conflicts between students, between principals and teachers, between teachers or even between the school unit and the local government or parents (Thanos, 2017). The bonds between conflict and education might be viewed in several ways. First and foremost, one can look into the roots of conflicts, such as inequality, ethnicity or gender-based violence, and see where education is implicated in such social phenomena. Secondly, it is possible to examine the repercussions of violent conflict on education itself. Thirdly, what can also be examined is the direct impact of modern school curricula and organization on conflicts. Last but not least, it is considered appropriate to examine the strategic educational responses during the conflict as well as after the conflict, in the reconstruction phase as well as the resolution of conflicts within the school environment (Davies, 2021).

3. School mediation in conflict resolution

The elements and the role of mediation may sound very nice and easy, but the teacher faces problems in his/her role as a mediator especially in modern societies, due to their multiculturalism and value pluralism. For instance, major difficulties arise in this context regarding his/her work from, on the one hand, disharmonies between the claims and norms of the state or the expectations of the various reference groups (parents, students as well as various social bodies) and, on the other hand, his own interpretation or self-perception. This often leads the teacher to role conflicts and a feeling of insecurity, as proven by a lot of studies and research (Sheridan, et al., 2017, Sani, 2015, Kruger, & Michalek, 2011).

Essentially, the process of communication between the school and the students' parents mainly depends on the principal of the school community and must be pursued in order for these two bodies to jointly search for the real causes as well as the effective solutions to the students' problems.

According to the systemic approach of the school unit, the principal must communicatively coordinate, in both the internal and external environment, people who have different personalities, social and cultural origins, opinions and attitudes as well as different ethics. Quite frequently, the different approach and interpretation of messages may potentially lead to communication problems that might lead to conflicts. The comprehension, interpretation and compromise of verbal and non-verbal messages with all members of the school community is the key to achieving the goals set by the principal at the beginning of the school year.

Both communication and cooperation between parents and teachers are deemed crucial in the learning process. However, they should be developed within the context of mutual respect and mutual understanding. It is very easy for a simple briefing to turn into a conflict when there is no convergent approach in their attitudes. Educator and parent may hold different viewpoints on the learning approach, the expectations and the evaluation of a child (Nova-Kaltsouni, 2004). There are teachers who support the dissociation of their responsibilities from the communication with parents (Matsangouras & Poulos, 2009). Thus, they attribute to parents a supporting role regarding the learning process and school performance, ignoring the fact that a lot of parents focus their interest on the general image of their child, which concerns his/her learning development, personality cultivation and social acceptance. There are also parents who underestimate the teachers' work and use offensive language about them even in front of their children and, as a result, the latter do not respect their teachers and misbehave inside and outside the classroom (Matsangouras & Verdis, 2003).

The principal of the school unit, within the implementation of his/her coordination duties, develops communication relationships with the school's teaching board and technical personnel, the students, the principals of neighboring schools, the Parents and Guardians Association, local bodies and clubs, the School Counselor and the Director of Primary or Secondary Education (Tzotzou & Anastasopoulos, 2013). An important component in these

communication relationships is the development of a positive climate, which assists cooperation, trust and facilitates interaction between them (Saitis, 2002). Despite the importance of these communication relationships, the present study will focus on the principal's communication with the children's parents. Parents have entrusted the school with the education, training and education of their children, with the aim of equipping them with knowledge and values, suitable for choosing higher studies, which will lead them to the labor market and their integration into today's society. Parents are therefore the people who are into the direct social environment of the school. A sound cooperation between school and family will help the family and the school to realize their goals with the children's progress always as a priority.

4. Research Methodology

4.1. Research Aim

The research process of the present paper constitutes a result of the literature review that preceded it. The main aim of the research process is to investigate effective leadership in decision-making and mediation in the relationship between teachers and parents. The aim of the research is to record the opinions of state primary school teachers regarding leadership in school units. However, what is also researched is the characterization degree of leadership in the school unit principals and the traits and characteristics they must possess for the necessary settlement of conflicts between parents and teachers. The main aim of this research, through the analysis of the research results, is to capture the core characteristics that a school unit should have with positive thinking, sound judgment and proper management by its teachers and principals.

4.2. Research population and sample

The procedure for compiling the sample was systematic sampling with a random sample, though with the limitation of its demographic classification, as the sample was selected from Western Macedonia. The method of systematic sampling was considered appropriate as it enables generalization of the results which become more representative of the population (Martin, 2008). The research involved teachers regardless of employment status (permanent and substitute ones), from primary schools in Western Macedonia. A total of 222 teachers participated, ranging in age from 20 to over 50. Principals, deputy principals and non-executive teachers also participated in the research, which is a key feature of the research that enables the study of opinions from all levels and jobs in the school unit. The majority of the sample was of Greek origin.

4.3. Research instrument

The research strategy followed for data collection was carried out using the method of quantitative research with sampling. Therefore, a questionnaire structured on questions from other researches with similar topics was chosen as a research tool (Saitis, 2001; Saitis, 2002; Stravakou, 2003; Sergiovanni, 1996; Pasiardis, 2004; Stamatis, 2005; Everard, Morris & Wilson, 2004; Kambouridis, 2002; Mademlis, 2014; Mukhopadhyay, 2005; Mylonas, 2005). It was compiled by the research designer, supervised by relevant teachers, digitized via Google Forms™ and distributed for completion. It was divided into four categories with closed-ended multiple-choice questions. There were eleven in the first category, of demographic interest, five multiple-choice ones in the second, which related to the communication skills and strategies of the principal during interventions and were structured according to the Likert scale, (1= Not at all, 5= A Lot). The third category, with four questions was structured on the same five-point scale 1-5 from "Not at all" to "A Lot", which concerned the importance of the role of the Principal in the communication relationships between teachers and parents in combination with a multiple choice one of three decision options (No-Yes-No Answer). In the fourth category, the principal's communication orientation with the resources of the Mediator was investigated, with four questions on the same five-point Likert scale, with the same multiple-choice options.

4.4. Data analysis methodology

Two parts were formed in the process of analyzing the data. In the first part, a descriptive analysis of the data was conducted and in the second part an inductive analysis was carried out.

In the part of the descriptive analysis, frequency tables and diagrams (bar graph and pie) were used to present the basic demographic characteristics of the sample. This part is particularly important as it provides the general picture of the sample and provides significant information about the participants, which can be used for the individual analysis. The opinions held by the teachers regarding the individual characteristics of control, such as interpersonal relationships in intervention situations, its role in the communication relationships between teachers and parents, and the communication orientation with the resources of mediation, were presented in summary tables.

In the second part of the data analysis, appropriate research tools were used in order to answer the research questions posed above. Non-parametric analysis was used for the correlation of variables using the variable comparison statistics for categorical variables of more than two categories, Kruskal-Wallis at a significance level of 5%. Non-parametric discriminant analysis was applied to create the categories in the principal's characteristics for the purposes of the last research question. Finally, factor analysis was applied to create the categories for the main characteristics that a principal should have in the role of Mediator during his/her intervention in the communication between parents and teachers.

Data entry, processing and analysis were performed by means of the statistical program IBMStatisticsSPSSversion 21.

5. Statistical analysis conclusions

The main communication techniques and skills possessed by a principal towards the completion of his/her interventions were concluded to be the ability to shape a positive climate and culture in the school and the ability to organize and coordinate responsibilities. According to the research participants, the appropriate strategies for effective intervention refer to cooperation and team spirit. Principals must be peacemakers and rationalize stressful situations through dialogue, making the people involved confront the problem. The moves s/he will have to follow in order to organize his/her actions should include meetings with an organized discussion topic and constant supervision and monitoring of the relationships between parents and teachers. The principal's role should be active and energetic rather than observative. However, his interventionist tendency should not be regular but limited to meetings once a month or three months. The action taken by principals in the schools where the research teachers work proved to satisfy their demands to a significant extent. Along with communication skills and strategies, they seem to use non-verbal skills as well. Nevertheless, parents did not seem to react positively to the role of mediator. When further analyzing the opinions held by groups of participants' characteristics, some significant results arose. There appeared to be a conflict in the views held by executives and non-executives regarding the implementation of innovative methods in interventions. The executives turned out to be supporters of the innovation, while the teachers did not seem to support it. Differences were also observed in the opinions held by teachers in small and large school units with regard to the encouragement of good relationships between parents and teachers. In small educational units, where the management and monitoring of disturbed relations between teachers and parents is more distinct, it seemed to be deemed more necessary than in large school units. During factor analysis, there emerged two important characteristics that a manager has to possess for the effectiveness of his interventions in the role of mediator. These characteristics were the participation of parents and teachers in problem solving and the individual information and action taken by the principal in order to effectively mediate in the restoration of relationships.

Table 1: Communication skills and strategies in order to manage interventions effectively

	A little	Moderately	Quite much	A lot
Ability to encourage positive relationships between teachers and parents	0 0%	10 4,5%	72 32,4%	140 63,1%
Decisiveness in taking initiatives	1 0,50%	8 3,6%	57 25,7%	156 70,3%
Ability to organise discussions between teachers-parents	1 0,5%	17 7,7%	83 37,4%	121 54,5%
Ability to create a positive atmosphere and culture in the school	0 0%	5 2,3%	48 21,6%	169 76,1%
Innovation	0 0%	25 11,3%	97 43,7%	100 45%
Good knowledge of educational legislation	0 0%	8 3,6%	54 24,3%	160 72,1%
Organisational skills and coordination of responsibilities	0 0%	3 1,4%	54 24,3%	165 74,3%

What came to prominence as an interesting conclusion of the research was the discrepancy in the views held by teachers and executives regarding the parental response to the intervention made by the principals. The teachers, who are invited to participate as directly involved ones in the interventions, stated that the response by parents and teachers during the intervention is negative, a fact which was not noticed by the executives.

Finally, from the factor analysis made in order to highlight the main characteristics that a principal must have in the role of mediator, the findings included cooperation, organization, use of body language, practical applications, forcefulness of character, ethics, training and briefing.

6. Final conclusions

The school leader plays the most important role in the common path shared by both school and parents as well as in the existence of constructive communication and collaboration, since s/he has a vision and exercises leadership and influence on his team, not from an authority position, but from a deeply human relationship one. The need for communication and collaboration between school leadership and parents is considered crucial by the majority of teachers, as long as their roles are clarified, since harmonious cooperation and effective communication facilitates the holistic development of students. Consequently, the school-family and by extension school leader and parents' relationship constitute a highly important chapter for children's education, the family itself and the relationships that regulate its members.

The school leader, in the broad sense of the term, is described as the most important member of the school for the implementation of the bidirectional communication within the school unit. S/he is responsible for communicating in a clear manner with all members of the school unit (students, teachers, parents) since a/he exercises influence which is exerted through deep human relationships and not through positions of authority. The concern refers to the leader's individualized contact with each and every parent, to personal attention, interpersonal communication, support and trust. It is essential that s/he have self-esteem, self-confidence, self-discipline as well as problem-solving, emotional intelligence and decision-making skills.

As far as the research part is concerned, with regard to the demographic characteristics, most of the entire sample were male, the largest percentage, about one in two, belonging to the age group of 50 years and above. In terms of employment status, the vast majority were permanent teachers. Most of them work in large school units and have a working experience of more than five years, while they reported that they did not hold an administrative position in their school unit. In terms of educational level, the largest proportion owned a university degree, while about a

third of them had a postgraduate degree and a small proportion of our sample were PhD holders. The percentages are almost evenly split in terms of place of work, with the proportion of those working in an urban area being slightly higher. As for the ones holding an administrative position, the largest proportion reported that they had been holding this position for over eight years. Finally, in relation to their service as deputy teachers, the largest proportion stated that it had been less than four years.

Figure 1: Participants' Gender

Table 2: Demographic Characteristics

		Frequencies	Percentages
Age	20-25	2	0,9%
	26-30	12	5,4%
	31-40	37	16,7%
	41-50	58	26,1%
	50+	113	50,9%
Employment Status	Permanent	193	86,9%
	Deputy	27	12,2%
	Hourly Employee	1	0,5%
	Unemployed	1	0,5%
Origin	Hellenic	221	99,5%
	Not Hellenic	1	0,5%
Do you belong to a big or small school unit?	Big	135	60,8%
	Small	87	39,2%
Work history at your current school	1 year	32	14,4%
	1-5 years	53	23,9%
	>5 years	137	61,7%
Executive position	Principal	48	21,6%
	Deputy Principal	18	8,1%
	Non-executive	156	70,3%

Regarding the strategies followed by principals in order to manage interventions, the main activities that were considered important by the majority of the teachers in the survey as key actions, involved planning responsibilities and meetings between students and teachers, organizing the content of teacher-parent meetings and monitoring teacher-parent relationships.

Table 3: Strategies followed by principals in order to manage interventions

S/he plans the responsibilities and meetings between student-teachers	N	20	28	67	64	43
	%	9%	12,6%	30,2%	28,8%	19,4%
S/He organises the content of teacher-parent meetings	N	24	38	67	53	40
	%	10,8%	17,1%	30,2%	23,9%	18%
S/he controls teacher-parent relationships	N	21	55	70	46	30
	%	9,5%	24,8%	31,5%	20,7%	13,5%

As for the principal's actions taken so as to manage interventions, most respondents consider them to be highly important. In order for problematic situations to be solved through dialogue-calmness and developed analytical thinking, most believe that discussions should be held quarterly. Furthermore, most teachers believe that their/principal's role in teacher-parent communication relationships is most important.

The principal, in addition to speaking to counselees, uses hand signals to a moderate extent. Moreover, as for his/her tone of voice, most of them answered that it is significant to a great extent, as is eye communication and finally, regarding facial expressions, most of them answered that is important be to a moderate extent. The teachers' responses were positive regarding the use of non-verbal behaviour with the aim of developing a positive emotional climate.

Table 4: Frequency table about the frequency of using communication media accompanied by speech for the direct assessment of the counselees

	Not at all	A little	Moderately	Quite much	A lot
Using hand signs	7	20	108	69	18
	3,2%	9%	48,6%	31,1%	8,1%
Voice tone	4	15	73	95	35
	1,8%	6,8%	32,9%	42,8%	15,8%
Eye communication	7	16	55	99	45
	3,2%	7,2%	24,8%	44,6%	20,3%
Facial Expressions	16	37	93	62	14
	7,2%	16,7%	41,9%	27,9%	6,3%

Regarding the section on the principal's communicative orientation with the mediator's skills and the willingness of parents and teachers to accept him/her as a mediator, the highest percentage answered a lot. As to whether the teams are weakened in the case of the existence of mediation by the principal in the parent-teacher communication, most of them think that this is not the case. Most were positive regarding the willingness of the principal to listen to the interlocutor and take an interest in him/her.

Table 5: Frequency table on parents' and teachers' willingness to accept the principal as a mediator

To what extent do you think that teachers and parents are "open" to accepting their principal's role as a mediator?	Not at all	A little	Moderately	Quite much	A lot
Frequencies	7	21	97	83	14
Percentages	3,2%	9,5%	43,7%	37,4%	6,3%

Concluding our section of questions about the skills that the principal as a mediator should have, concerning the developed skills the respondents answered that they should be highly developed, and so they did with regard to continuous training and participation in appropriate training programmes, dealing with problems directly and timely and generating culture. Finally, as for the implementation of actions with the participation of teachers and parents, the highest percentage answered positively to a large extent.

Table 6: Frequency table on the principal's skills regarding the role of mediator

	To minimum extent	a little extent	To moderate extent	a large extent	To great extent
Developed collaboration skills	1 0,5%	0 0%	11 5%	81 36,5%	129 58,1%
Continuous training and participation in appropriate training programmes	0 0%	4 1,8%	31 14%	91 41%	96 43,2%
Direct and timely problem tackling	0 0%	0 0%	6 2,7%	73 32,9%	143 64,4%
Collaborative leadership model	0 0%	2 0,9%	15 6,8%	90 40,5%	115 51,8%
Promotion of culture	1 0,5%	3 1,4%	26 11,7%	94 42,3%	98 44,1%
Implementation of actions involving teachers and parents	1 0,5%	5 2,3%	56 25,2%	88 39,6%	72 32,4%

The decisiveness in taking initiatives was described as highly important by all respondents, with deputy principals agreeing with this perspective to a greater extent. What was rated as a very important communication skill by all the respondents was the ability to create a positive climate and culture in the school with the principals and deputy principals considering it quite important. For deputy principals, innovation was characterized to be highly important and so it was for principals with a slightly lower percentage, followed by executives of no position with even lower percentages. On the contrary, non-executives consider the good knowledge of educational legislation very important which is followed in this answer by the principals and with a slight difference by the vice-principals. Finally, the diligence and coordination of responsibilities are mentioned by non-executives, followed by the deputy principals and lastly by the principals.

Table 7: Relevance table and independence test on principals', deputy principals' and non-executives' views on the principal's key communication skills and strategies during the interventions

		Principal	Deputy principal	Non-executive	R	p
Ability to foster positive relationships between teachers and parents	Moderately	0 0,00%	0 0,00%	10 6,40%	0,104	0,308
	Quite much	17 35,40%	5 27,80%	50 32,10%		
	A lot	31 64,60%	13 72,20%	96 61,50%		
Decisiveness in taking initiatives	A little	0 0,00%	0 0,00%	1 0,60%	0,128	0,301
	Moderately	0 0,00%	2 11,10%	6 3,80%		
	Quite much	15 31,30%	2 11,10%	40 25,60%		

ability to create a positive climate and culture in the school	A lot	33	14	109		
		68,80%	77,80%	69,90%		
	Moderately	0	0	5	0,091	0,456
		0,00%	0,00%	3,20%		
Innovation	Quite much	13	5	30		
		27,10%	27,80%	19,20%		
	A lot	35	13	121		
		72,90%	72,20%	77,60%		
Good knowledge of educational legislation	Moderately	3	1	21	0,174	0,009*
		6,30%	5,60%	13,50%		
	Quite much	15	5	77		
		31,30%	27,80%	49,40%		
Organizational skills and coordination of responsibilities	A lot	30	12	58		
		62,50%	66,70%	37,20%		
	Moderately	4	1	3	0,127	0,128
		8,30%	5,60%	1,90%		
Organizational skills and coordination of responsibilities	Quite much	14	6	34		
		29,20%	33,30%	21,80%		
	A lot	30	11	119		
		62,50%	61,10%	76,30%		
Organizational skills and coordination of responsibilities	moderately	1	0	2	0,122	0,158
		2,10%	0,00%	1,30%		
	Quite much	18	3	33		
		37,50%	16,70%	21,20%		
Organizational skills and coordination of responsibilities	A lot	29	15	121		
		60,40%	83,30%	77,60%		

In our inferential analysis and in attempting to determine the importance of the principal's role in the teacher-parent interpersonal relationships in relation to school location, no statistically significant differences emerged between the two groups. As far as the size of the school unit and the principals' communication skills are concerned, a significant dependency was discernible. Also, the ability to encourage good relationships between teachers and parents in small school units is considered more imperative compared to large ones.

The participants in our research effort pinpointed a statistically significant dependence between the communication skill and strategy of good educational legislation knowledge and the size of the school unit. It still emerges is that good knowledge of educational legislation in large school units is considered more important compared to smaller ones.

In order for principals to apply effective leadership in decision-making, conciliation and mediation, it is necessary, according to the vice principals, to have skills and continuous training and participation in appropriate training programmes, immediate and timely problem-solving and implementation of actions in which teachers and parents are involved. For teachers who do not hold an executive position, when it comes to the principal in the role of facilitator, it is necessary that s/he possess developed collaboration skills and implement a collaborative leadership model.

Regarding the investigation of the communication strategies followed by the principals, the sample of participants selected was the one who responded positively to the question whether the school principal is willing to listen to his/her interlocutor and is interested in him/her and they indicated that the most popular form of communication is body language, followed by eye communication.

To investigate the degree of influence regarding the application of communication skills by the principal on the response of parents and teachers, it arose that as the frequency of implementing specific actions (communication skills and the degree of willingness of parents to cooperate) increases, the response of parents and teachers decreases. On the other hand, when principals/teachers work with the parents' association in order to mediate, in cases where there is no cooperative climate between the school and parents, parents and teachers respond more positively.

In additions, the role of the principal as a mediator by means of using communication techniques and mediation skills was investigated in terms of the empowerment or disempowerment felt by the parent-teachers. It was observed that as the more frequently these mediation strategies using communication techniques and skills are implemented, the more disempowered the groups resorting to the principal/teacher for mediation feel.

In general, it is concluded that principals who take on the role of mediator perceive that their role is positively responded to be effective for both parents and teachers. In contrast, deputy principals and teachers who are recipients of the role rather than agents perceive that the response is not positive and the principal's role does not promote efficiency.

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